

Decoding Niobium Carbide MXene Dual-Functional Photoactive Cathode in Photo-Enhanced Hybrid Zinc-Ion Capacitor

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Coupling of energy harvesting and storage discrete modules in a single architecture as a “two-in-one” concept is significant in off-grid energy storage devices. This approach can decrease the device size and the loss of energy transmission in the common integrated energy harvesting and storage systems. This work systematically investigates the photoactive characteristics of niobium carbide MXene, Nb₂CT_x, in a photo-enhanced hybrid zinc-ion capacitor (P-ZIC). The unique configuration of the Nb₂CT_x photoactive cathode absorbs light to charge the capacitor and enables it to operate continuously in light-powered mode. The Nb₂CT_x-based P-ZIC shows a photo-driven capacitance enhancement of over 60% at the scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ under 50 mW cm⁻² illumination with 435 nm wavelength. Furthermore, a photo-enhanced specific capacitance of ~ 27 F g⁻¹, an impressive photo-charging voltage response of 1.0 V, and capacitance retention of ~85% (over 3,000 cycles) are obtained.

Exploration of light-matter interactions particularly in off-grid energy storage systems has garnered considerable attention recently.¹ This heightened interest is due to the recognition that light can either fully charge electrochemical energy storage systems or significantly develop their performances (i.e., quicker charging rates, and capacitance enhancement).^{3, 4} To have a robust architecture and highly efficient platform for a photo-enhanced energy storage system, researchers are actively investigating materials possessing both simultaneously active optical and electrochemical properties.⁵⁻⁷ This dual functionality enables the light harvesting and storage of solar energy within the same material and components. Hence, numerous demonstrations for enhancing the performance of energy storage devices through light are being under investigation in various energy storage systems like lithium (Li)-ion batteries,⁸⁻¹⁰ Li-air batteries,^{11, 12} and capacitors.^{13, 14} Among them, there is a specific focus on the study of photo-enhanced divalent zinc (Zn)-ion and magnesium (Mg)-ion batteries and capacitors as the most promising energy storage technologies.^{15, 16} Because Zn and Mg anodes have unique features such as low cost of Zn,¹⁷ and natural abundance of Mg,¹⁸ superior safety,^{19, 20} high specific capacity including 820 mAh g⁻¹ and 5851 mAh cm⁻³ for Zn,²¹ 2205 mAh g⁻¹ and 3833 mAh cm⁻³ for Mg,²² low redox potential ($E_{Zn} = -0.76$ V vs standard hydrogen electrode),²³ and long-term stability.^{24, 25} Nevertheless, the kinetics of Mg-ion energy storage systems tend to be sluggish compared to monovalent ions like Li.¹⁶ Hence, this work presents a ground-breaking effort on a hybrid Zn-ion capacitor with 2D niobium carbide (Nb₂CT_x) MXene as a dual-functional photoactive electrode material capable of driving light enhancement while at the same time storing charges. The hypothesis of Nb₂CT_x MXene selection is due to its narrow bandgap (~ 0.81 eV) belonging to the transition metal carbide core (Nb₂C),²⁶ and the bandgap value of ~ 1.3 eV mainly comes from the formation of niobium dioxide (NbO₂) surface layer.²⁷

These two phases make the Nb₂CT_x MXene a powerful nanostructure electrode material for simultaneous light harvesting and charge storage. **Figures 1a–1d** indicate the crystal phase, structure, and morphology of the Nb₂CT_x MXene characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). It has been demonstrated by XRD that aluminium (Al) layers of the Nb₂AlC MAX phase were almost completely etched during the synthesis of Nb₂CT_x with only one remaining moderate peak at $2\theta = 12.8^\circ$ corresponding to starting MAX phase, resulting in a multilayer structure of Nb₂CT_x. Raman characterization demonstrates the vibrational modes of Nb₂CT_x at six main Raman shifts specified in **Figure 1b**. SEM and EDS of the Nb₂CT_x confirm the layered structure of the sample including a trace of Al as well as –O and –F terminals (**Figures 1c** and **1d**). **Figure 1e** depicts an optical image (inset), SEM, and EDS of the Nb₂CT_x-based slurry that was synthesized by carbon black and PVDF (see **Supporting Information**). The slurry was synthesized for the next steps to determine its localized electrochemical reactivity, optoelectronic properties, and electrochemical behavior of the Nb₂CT_x as a photocathode material. **Figures 1f** and **1g** display 3D topographic representations of the current distribution near the surface of the Nb₂CT_x-based slurry mixture. The figures include values for roughness (z) and current at the tip of the ultramicroelectrode (UME). Both of roughness (geometry) and physical properties (i.e., conductivity) of the material influence the measured current in feedback mode. When the UME is positioned near the surface of an insulating material, the hemispherical diffusion layer is obstructed, resulting in a reduction of current. Conversely, as the UME approaches a conductive (or electrochemically active) surface despite the hindered hemispherical diffusion layer the current increases due to the regeneration of the mediator within the electrolyte.²⁸ Since the contribution of the roughness to the overall measured current is negligible, the obtained positive feedback currents in scanning electrochemical microscopy measurement of Nb₂CT_x in the designated area are caused by the conductive properties of the sample and substrate. The obtained

current values of the dried slurry made by the Nb_2CT_x sample inside of the cavity are mainly similar in magnitude to the SiO_2 substrate surrounding the sample. Nonetheless, few peaks of measured current were observed (four highlighted red circles in **Figure 1h**) over the surface of the slurry indicating increased regeneration of the $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ redox reaction in comparison to the SiO_2 . These points also were confirmed by SEM and EDS analyses.

Figure 1. (a) XRD pattern, (b) Raman spectrum, (c and d) SEM and EDS analyses of the synthesized Nb_2CT_x MXene powder. (e) SEM, optical image (inset), and EDS analyses of the Nb_2CT_x -based slurry. (f-h) 3D topographical mapping catalytic activity of drop-casted Nb_2CT_x -based slurry, roughness (z), and current value, as well as SEM and EDS analyses of the examined four circle points indicated on 2D topographical mapping.

To evaluate the optoelectronic and initial electrochemical characteristics of the Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode, a self-powered photo-detector device was set up in a beaker cell using a three-electrode system (**Figure 2a**). To do so, as shown in **Figure 2a**, around $10 \mu\text{l}$ of the as-prepared Nb_2CT_x -based slurry was drop-casted on a flexible and transparent polyethylene terephthalate-coated indium tin oxide ($\sim 80 \text{ nm}$) and gold ($\sim 20 \text{ nm}$) (PET-coated ITO/Au) substrate. Then, a drop of Nafion ($\text{C}_7\text{HF}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{S}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{F}_4$) was deployed on top of the electrode to form a stable structure within the following tests. The optoelectronic and electrochemical efficiencies of the Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode were tested in both dark and illumination conditions by a LED with $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$ and an intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} . **Figure 2b** demonstrates the energy band diagram and energetically favorable passage for the photogenerated electrons in the Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode after illumination.

Figure 2. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation of Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode constructed on PET-coated ITO/Au substrate, and the three-electrode cell setup. (b) Schematic demonstration of the energy band diagram and energetically favorable trajectory of the prepared Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode. (c) Current-time plot with repeated dark and illumination conditions at 0 applied voltage. (d) Schematic illustrates the generated current versus time because of two pyroelectric and photoelectric effects under illumination and dark pulses. (e) Current-voltage plots under dark and illumination conditions at a low scan rate of 5 mA s⁻¹. (f) Cyclic voltammogram at different scan rates and evaluation of double layer capacitance plot of the Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode under dark conditions.

It can be seen that both Nb₂C and NbO₂ possess lower bandgap values than the energy of the illuminated $\lambda = 435$ nm light with ~ 2.85 eV. As a result, photogenerated electrons could drift from NbO₂ and Nb₂C toward PET-coated ITO/Au through additive carbon black and propagate in the system. Therefore, the separated electrons and holes tend to adsorb the hydrated Zn²⁺ cations and SO₄²⁻ anions of the ionized ZnSO₄ aqueous electrolyte. The current-time plot of the three-cell system under periodic illumination at zero applied voltage is shown in **Figure 2c**. The current signal exhibits an immediate increase upon exposure to light, followed by a decrease upon turning off the light. Notably, there is an absence of a steady state current during both illuminated and dark periods. This recognized behavior in current is ascribed to the pyroelectric effect (**Figure 2d**), probably because of the NbO₂ phase in the MXene sample.²⁹ However, the photocurrent gradually stabilizes over time and reaches a constant value. This stabilization is primarily due to the diminishing pyroelectric polarization potential caused by a steady-state temperature ($dT/dt = 0$, $T =$ temperature, $t =$ time). A similar pattern is also observed upon switching off the LED light. The linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) characteristic of the photocathode was performed in dark and illumination conditions to further assess the photocurrent behavior. **Figure 2e** illustrates a higher current value over the all-applied voltage range under illumination compared to the dark condition. This activity indicates the optimal photosensitivity behavior of Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode for the generation and separation of electrons and holes with a result in the formation of a higher photocurrent. The generated photocurrent by the Nb₂CT_x-based electrode in chronoamperometry characterization (~ 0.2 μA) is different from LSV (~ 1.5 μA). This difference in photocurrent could be due to a higher level of stability and constancy of the current response over time by chronoamperometry in comparison to LSV. The current response stability by chronoamperometry arises from the fact that the applied voltage is constant throughout the experimental procedure and this keeps the material stable within the test. Nevertheless, the applied voltage fluctuates during LSV analyses with an electrochemical process occurring on the electrode material within the applied voltage range, rendering the electrode less stable. Thus, the different current responses recognized by these two techniques can be ascribed to the distinct measurement parameters and the various electrochemical processes taking place on the electrode material. The energy storage capability of the Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode was also determined through the three-electrode system. This was done by the CV responses at various scan rates within the working voltage of 0.0 to 0.5 V (**Figure 2f**). The selection of this relatively low working voltage range was due to blocking any gas formation. Notably, the

current density reaches 0.2 mA cm^{-2} at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} , while the double-layer capacitance attains a value of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ } \mu\text{F}$ at 0.2 V . In the next step, the as-prepared Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode was assembled inside a printed holder with an optical window of 8 mm diameter as a photo-enhanced hybrid zinc-ion capacitor (P-ZIC) cell to evaluate energy storage mechanism and performance under dark and illumination conditions (**Figure 3a**).

Initially, dark- and photo-current efficiency of the Nb_2CT_x -based P-ZIC was analyzed using light-dependent chronoamperometry in dark and illuminated conditions. Three different LEDs of $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$ (intensity of 25 and 50 mW cm^{-2} , at $0, 0.2, 1$, and OCP applied voltages, OCP = 0.93 V), $\lambda = 533 \text{ nm}$ (intensity of 50 and 100 mW cm^{-2} , at 0 applied voltage), and $\lambda = 630 \text{ nm}$ (intensity of 50 and 100 mW cm^{-2} , at 0 applied voltage) were employed for this purpose (**Figures S1 and S2, Supporting Information**). It is distinguished that the maximum photocurrent response ($\Delta I = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}$) was for $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$. Hence, $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$ was selected for the next characterization to determine the performance of the P-ZIC.

Figure 3. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation of Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode, the two-electrode cell setup under dark and illumination conditions. (b) Photo-charged ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 50 mW cm^{-2} , at 0.02 mA cm^{-2}) and dark-discharged (at different specific current rates) of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC. (c) Photo-charged and photo-discharged ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 50 mW cm^{-2} , at 0.02 mA cm^{-2}), and dark-discharged (at 0.02 mA cm^{-2}) of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC. (d) Cyclic photo-charged ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 50 mW cm^{-2} , at 0.03 mA cm^{-2}) and dark-discharged (at 0.06 mA cm^{-2}) behavior of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC at its initial 10 cycles.

Next, the P-ZIC was photo-charged with a light intensity of 50 mW cm^{-2} , a low current density of 0.02 mA cm^{-2} , at the voltage range of 0.2 - 1.0 V , and then discharged by galvanostatic at different specific current rates (**Figure 3b**). That specific voltage range was optimized to avoid any dehydration of electrolyte ions by hydrogen evolution reduction and oxygen evolution reaction (**Figure S3, Supporting Information**). It can be seen that the photo-charging voltage response of the cell reaches the cut-off voltage of 1.0 V after $\sim 350 \text{ s}$, which is greater than the most recent reports of photo-enhanced capacitors (**Table S1, Supporting Information**). To assess the photo-charge, photo-discharge, and dark-discharge behavior of the cell in further detail, the P-ZIC was charged under illumination and then discharged at two situations of illumination and dark with the same scan rates (0.02 mA cm^{-2}) (**Figure 3c**). The P-ZIC advantages from a constant flow of photons throughout the photo-charge and photo-discharge states with facilitate in continuous generation of electron-hole pairs. As a result, the charge transfer is accelerated with a faster charging compared to the discharging when light energy continues to generate electron-hole pairs. Albeit, the photovoltaic influence stays passive in the dark mode with no ongoing creation of electron-hole pairs. Hence, the discharge process of the capacitor relies entirely on the stored charge process. **Figure S4 (Supporting Information)** also depicts the photo-charging of the P-ZIC under a voltage-floating condition with a very low current density of 0.006 mA cm^{-2} where it attains $\sim 0.96 \text{ V}$ after $\sim 1000 \text{ s}$. The initial cycling stability of the P-ZIC was also examined by applying ten repeated photo-charging (50 mW cm^{-2} , 0.03 mA cm^{-2}) and galvanostatic discharging (0.06 mA cm^{-2}) (**Figures 3d**). A steady state photo-charge and galvanostatic discharge activity was detected during the cycling.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge-discharge (CD) characterizations were performed on the P-ZIC under dark and illumination (25 and 50 mW cm^{-2}) conditions at different scan rates to estimate energy storage performance. The CVs show pseudo-capacitive features with intercalation and partial oxidation-reduction (redox) (**Figures 4a–4d, Figures S5a and S5b, Supporting**

Information). This energy storage mechanism is similar to a battery-type intercalation process,³⁰ with a difference in fast reaction kinetics specific to a supercapacitor electrode. The redox peaks can refer to the reversible redox reaction that is accomplished at the Zn anode during charge-discharge cycles with this statement that Zn^{+2} ions are removed from the anode and transferred to the electrolyte with releasing $2e^-$ throughout charging. Concurrently, there will not be any typical redox reaction in the cathode except SO_4^{2-} adsorption and storing electrostatically.

Figure 4. (a-d) Comparative CV analyses of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC at different specified scan rates under dark, 25 mW cm^{-2} (dark orange), and 50 mW cm^{-2} (light orange) illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$) conditions. (e) Diagram of the capacity enhancement under illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$) with 25 and 50 mW cm^{-2} intensities versus different scan rates. (f-h) Comparative CD analyses of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC at different identified specific currents under dark, 25 mW cm^{-2} (light orange), and 50 mW cm^{-2} (dark orange) illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$) conditions. (i) Comparative specific capacitance at different specific currents under dark and illumination conditions with specified light intensities on the figure. (j-l) Nyquist plots and equivalent circuit diagrams of the Nb_2CT_x -based photo-E ZIC in dark and illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 50 mW cm^{-2}) conditions.

A reverse redox reaction occurs during discharging with the movement of Zn^{+2} back onto the anode and releasing the stored SO_4^{2-} from the cathode into the electrolyte to complete the cycle. These redox reactions in the anode, along with the cathode's electrostatic behavior and photogenerated electrons and holes, contribute to the energy storage capabilities of photo-E ZIC. It can be seen from CV results that light in both applied intensities effectively enhance the storage efficiency of the P-ZIC. The highest capacity enhancement calculated according to equation $\frac{C_{\text{light}} - C_{\text{dark}}}{C_{\text{dark}}} \times 100\%$ (C_{light} and C_{dark} , specific capacitances in illumination and dark, respectively) reaches above 60% with 50 mW cm^{-2} light intensity at the rate of 10 mV s^{-1} (**Figure 4e**). This capacity enhancement under illumination can be ascribed to the significant separation of photogenerated electrons and holes. This separation notably enhances the conductivity of the electrode materials, leading to a substantial increase in charge transport density and storage during the electrolytic process. **Figure 4e** also indicates the impact of light intensity, revealing that the capacity enhancement diminishes as the light intensity decreases to a lower level. The figure also highlights that capacity enhancement is reduced at the higher scan rates most probably due to insufficient time for generation of larger electron and holes as well as limited electrolyte ion diffusion. The CD characteristic behavior at different specific currents (**Figures 4f–4h**, **Figures S5c and S5d**, **Supporting Information**) also is in line with the CV results where it can be viewed that light enhances the charge and discharge times due to the generation of photoelectrons. Specific capacitance enhancement at different specific currents (**Figure 4i**) shows that the specific capacitance of P-ZIC overtakes $\sim 27 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ with 50 mW cm^{-2} light intensity at 30 mA g^{-1} specific current which is almost three times larger than dark condition and 1.5 greater than illumination status with 25 mW cm^{-2} intensity. To explore the characteristics of charge transport and ion diffusion, the Nyquist impedance spectra of the P-ZIC in dark and illumination (50 mW cm^{-2}) circumstances were first examined (**Figure 4j**), and then their Randles circuits were simulated with well-low errors of $\chi^2 = 0.01$ (dark) and $\chi^2 = 0.02$ (illumination) (**Figures 4k and 4l**). It is seen that the P-ZIC has a lower charge transfer resistance ($R_s = \sim 27 \Omega$) under illumination in comparison with the dark position ($R_s = \sim 30 \Omega$). This is evident from the shift of the overall resistance towards lower values during illumination because of larger photogenerated charge carriers. As stated by the fitted results, each circuit possesses an active electrolyte resistance (R_s) in series with a parallel blend of the charge transfer resistance (R_p) and constant phase element (CPE), relevant to the Nb_2CT_x -based photocathode. The

second part of each Randles circuit has an extra impedance (W) representing a faradaic reaction in addition to the previous elements. The impedance defines the ion diffusion, transport, and kinetics processes within the electrolyte.

The energy density, power density, and operation modes performance summary of the Nb₂CT_x-based P-ZIC were calculated in dark and illumination conditions at five different specific currents (**Figures 5a–5c**). It is observed that the energy density values are enhanced under illumination because of larger photogenerated charges and specific capacitance. However, the power density under illumination will remain at the same value in dark conditions. This effect corresponds to the discharge time value with light intensity. Once the light intensity increases, the discharge time value also will be enhanced with the same proportion because of the already vast storage charges. Hence, the power density [$P = (E \times 3600)/t$, E = energy density, and t = discharge time] will remain the same. The long-term capacity retention and Coulombic efficiency of Nb₂CT_x-based P-ZIC were performed over 3,000 cycles at a specific current of 100 mA g⁻¹ in the dark status (**Figure 5d**). The graph shows that the sample provides almost stable Coulombic efficiency. Albeit, the capacitance retention reaches ~ 85% after 3,000 cycles. Morphology and EDS characteristics of the Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode after stability were evaluated to find a reason for the ~ 15% reduction (**Figure S6a, Supporting Information**). The EDS results demonstrate a trace of sulfur and zinc relevant to the residual electrolyte and a large peak of fluorine due to the Nafion. Those residual zinc and sulfur elements most probably diminish the stability of the photocathode. A set of CV at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ and CD at a specific current of 75 mA g⁻¹ (**Figures S6b and S6c, Supporting Information**) were conducted on the P-ZIC in dark and illumination (50 mW cm⁻²) conditions to examine photo enhancement efficiency of the device after stability test. The findings indicate that, even though the photo enhancement efficiency of the P-ZIC diminishes after stability, it continues to play an efficient role in responding to light stimuli throughout the charge and discharge processes.

Figure 5. Calculated energy and power densities along with performance summary of operation modes at different specific currents under (a) dark, (b) illumination ($\lambda= 435$ nm) at 25 mW cm⁻², and (c) illumination ($\lambda= 435$ nm) at 50 mW cm⁻² on Nb₂CT_x-based photo-E ZIC. (d) Long-term cyclic stability of the Nb₂CT_x-based photo-E ZIC after 3,000 cycles.

In summary, this research presents a ground-breaking exploration into the development of dual-functional photoactive cathodes, introducing a novel approach to leveraging MXene-based materials for this purpose. The study highlights the effectiveness of Nb₂CT_x-based photocathode in P-ZIC, enabling direct charging through light absorption, and eliminating the need for external photovoltaic devices. The evaluation involved comparing the efficiency of the Nb₂CT_x-based P-ZIC to two distinct low light intensities of 25 and 50 mW cm⁻² with $\lambda= 435$ nm. The results exhibit a capacitance enhancement of over 60% under an intensity of 50 mW cm⁻². Moreover, the achievement presents an impressive output voltage of 1.0 V at the same light intensity. Further analysis of the fabricated P-ZIC also revealed a very good capacitance retention rate of ~ 85% after undergoing 3,000 charge-discharge cycles. This study anticipates the potential of MXene nanomaterials to not only provide a powerful single-architecture platform for new compact off-grid

energy storage devices but also be a perspective to expand additional new MXene-based nanostructures by their suitable surface chemistry modification for the next-generation flexible photo-enhanced energy storage devices. This anticipation is due to the mass production advantage of MXenes and their remarkable intrinsic properties. The characteristics with the potential to manufacture a simple and efficient device architecture compared to existing alternatives with integrated energy harvesting and energy storage segments.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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